

STRUCTURAL TESTING AND NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF A 34M COMPOSITE WIND TURBINE BLADE

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SUMMARY

A full-scale 34 m composite wind-turbine blade was tested to failure under flap-wise loading. Local displacement measurement equipment was developed and displacements were recorded throughout the loading history.

Ovalization of the load carrying box girder was measured in the full-scale test and simulated in non-linear FE-calculations. The non-linear Brazier effect, is characterized by a crushing pressure which cause the ovalization. To capture this effect, non-linear FE-analysis on different scales were employed. A global non-linear FE-model of the entire blade was prepared and the boundaries to a more detailed sub-model were extracted. The FE-model was calibrated based on full-scale test measurements.

Local displacement measurements identified the location of failure initiation which lead to catastrophic failure. Comparisons between measurements and FE-simulations showed that delamination of the outer skin was the initial failure mechanism followed by delamination buckling which then led to collapse.

KEYWORDS: Structural testing, wind turbine blades, non-linear finite element analysis, sub-modelling, failure mechanism, Brazier effect, anticlastic effect

INTRODUCTION

The size of wind turbine blades are expected to increase considerably in the future, demanding a better understanding of the structural behaviour on a different scale. Detailed structural behaviour must be investigated beyond the elastic range. This may include identification of failure modes which lead to ultimate collapse. Wind turbine blades have typically been optimized by experimental tests and analytical methods. However, numerical simulation tools are gaining wider acceptance as they become more sophisticated in their predictive capability as well as offering a route to significantly lower developmental costs.

NUMERICAL METHODS

The Finite Element Method (FEM) has traditionally been used in the development of wind turbine blades mainly to investigate the global behaviour in terms of e.g. eigen-frequencies, tip deflections, and global stress/strain levels. This type of FE-simulation usually predicts the global stiffness and stresses with a good accuracy. Local deformations and stresses are often more difficult to predict and little has been published in this area. One reason is that the local deformations and stresses can be non-linear, while globally these are linear (for small deflections). Another factor is that a relatively simple shell model can be used for representing the global behaviour, while a computationally more expensive 3D-solid model is necessary to predict the local behaviour.

Even with a full 3D solid model it would rarely be possible to predict deformations or stresses accurately without calibration of the FE model. This calibration is necessary due to large manufacturing tolerances. Features such as box girder corners and adhesive joints often differ from specifications. Geometric imperfections are often seen and can cause unexpected behaviour, especially relating to the strength predictions but also the local deformations can be affected. In this paper, box girder corners were not modelled in detail with solids. Instead, the rotational stiffness of the corners was calibrated with deflections measured in the full-scale test.

A big advantage of using FEM is that, once the model is set up and calibrated, complex load cases representing actual wind conditions can be analyzed. Only idealised loads can be imposed in a full-scale test and in this paper the critical flap-wise load case is evaluated.

FULL-SCALE TEST OF 34 M SSP- BLADE

A full-scale 34 m wind-turbine blade, manufactured by SSP-Technology A/S, was tested to failure under flap-wise loading as shown in Fig.1. The blade had passed all static and dynamic (correspond to 20 years life time) tests required by the classification bodies. The SSP-blade is made of glass-epoxy pre-preg material and is designed with a load carrying box girder, see figure 2.

Fig. 1: Full-Scale Test – Flap wise loading

Fig. 2: Blade with a load carrying main spar

Earlier experience from another full-scale test [1] and FE-simulations [2] has shown that the cap deflect non-linearly. The conclusion from these investigations is that the load carrying box girder ovalizes, when the blade bends flap-wise. New equipment has been developed to record the web deflection resulting from ovalization, see figure 3.

Figure 3: Local displacement equipment in a blade section

Each web sensor can independently measure in- and outward web deflection which occurs when the box girder ovalizes or is subjected to other types of deformation. In the eight-meter segment near the root, effects due to change in geometry interact with conventional ovalization effects resulting in a counterintuitive non-linear response. Mechanisms which explain these deformations and the relevance of including these effects are presented.

A combination of measurements and FE-simulation has shown that delamination of the outer skin was the initial failure mechanism followed by delamination buckling which led to collapse.

SUB-MODELLING TECHNIQUES

A local model, using shell and brick elements, was developed for a span-wise segment of the blade. The 0-13 m segment is found to be the most critical part and final failure also occurred in this section. The boundary conditions used in this sub-model were based on the displacement field taken from the global FE-model. Normally, the linear displacement field is used in sub-modelling techniques, but in this case this technique cannot be used, since the non-linear effect dominates. The explanation as to why the use of a nonlinear displacement field is required, even at moderate non-linearity, is given in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Deflections at the centre of the upper spar cap have been measured at seven different sections. In the section 10.3 m from the root three chord-wise locations were measured, as shown in figure 3.

New equipment for deflection measurement was developed for use inside the box girder. The equipment is shown in figure 3 and measures local web deflections with a fixed reference frame in the centre of the box girder. The central reference frame is telescopic to allow for change in section height during ovalization of the box girder.

Nonlinear geometric deformations

Different deformation patterns were observed during the full-scale test. The blade showed three distinct deformation patterns dependent on the span-wise location (all measured from the root):

- Root segment (0-4m)
- Transition segment (4-8m) from root to box girder segment
- Box girder segment (8-34m)

The first two segments will only be treated very briefly in this paper, but are included to illustrate the complexity of local deformations. Deformations in the root segment also influence the boundary conditions on the box girder segment, which starts 8m from the root. It should be noted that the box girder actually runs along the full length of the blade but behaves differently in the three segments describe in the following.

Root segment (0-4m)

Part of the web deformations are due to the gravity load, which causes the webs to show a non-symmetric behaviour before loading. This behaviour is specific to the SSP-blade, and is due to the change in box girder section geometry along the root segment.

Fig. 4a. Sketch of non-symmetric behaviour
Fig. 4b. Measurement -Non-symmetric behaviour

Non-symmetric web deflection is shown in figure 4a and measurements are shown in figure 4b. The measurements exclude deflections due to pre-load (gravity load) because the measuring gauges were reset prior to loading of the blade. The unusual behaviour of the webs is not discussed further here but is most likely related to the constraints imposed by the stiff root connection to the hub. In the current context, it is merely of interest to be able to apply the correct boundary conditions on the segments further away from the root.

Transition segment (4-8m)

A large change in cap curvature, and therefore cap height, is taken place in the transition segment, see figure 5a. Outward cap deformations were measured during the full-scale test as shown in figure 5b. These outward deflections were seen on the compression side of the blade and are linked to the rapid change in cap profile in this segment.

Figure 5a.
Changes in profile height

Figure 5b.
Outward cap deformation - measured

deformation - measured

Box girder segment (8-34m)

In this segment the expected ovalization caused by flapwise bending was observed. This nonlinear deformation or “flattening” of the cross section is also known as the Brazier effect [1] and is most pronounced for long thin hollow beams subjected to bending. The crushing pressure caused by the Brazier effect has a large effect on the web deflections and local deformation sensors have measured up to 20 mm displacement at the trailing web and 11 mm for leading web.

Figure 6. Crushing pressure from the Brazier effect

FINITE ELEMENT RESULTS

In this chapter results from the numerical modelling (FEM) will be presented. The main focus will be on the 8-13 m section, where the collapse occurred.

0–13 m sub-model

Capturing the correct deformation pattern required a more detailed sub-model of the 0-13 m section. The detailed sub-model includes solid elements in the webs and spar caps, see figure 7b.

Figure 7a. Global 34m FE-model

Figure 7b. 0-13 m sub-model

The main purpose of a global FE model of the whole blade is to provide representative boundaries for the 0-13m sub-model. Non-linear analysis is clearly necessary here due to the large deflections seen in the blade at higher loads. More interestingly, a combination of the anticlastic effect [3], which is a linear phenomenon, and the non-linear Brazier effect [4],[5] seems to counteract one another at certain locations along the blade. At small loads the anticlastic effect can cause outward cap deflection which then changes to inward deflection at higher loads as the Brazier effect (ovalization) takes over. This observation is illustrated in Figure 8. Linear analysis would simply not capture deflections due to the Brazier effect.

Figure 8. Non-linear response in global model

Calibration of corner stiffness in the FE-model

Working with large wind turbine blades, made of fibre composites, a large margin of production tolerances must be accepted. SSP-Technology A/S use a relative high quality production method (pre-preg without autoclave). Imperfections, such as voids, are most pronounced in areas where pre-preg layers terminate such as the corner of a box girder.

Figure 9a. Section through a box corner

Figure 9b. Box corner used for calibration

In principle all variations could be identified by cutting the blade into small pieces, measure the local stiffness, and then make a detailed FE-model which includes all these variations. In practise this is prohibitively expensive and a simpler approach was applied. Box girder corners in the FE-model were only represented with a coarse mesh of layered shell elements, which of course do not give the true picture of the corner stiffness. However, the modulus of an “adjustable” element was tuned to obtain the best fit with the actual deflections measured in the full-scale test.

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL TEST AND NUMERICAL MODELLING

Fig. 10a: Comparison of cap deflections

Fig. 10b: Comparison of web deflections

Comparing experimentally measured cap deflections with FE predictions, the agreement is found to be acceptable following calibration of the corner stiffness, see figure 10a. The web deflections, however, are not satisfactory above 80% load, see figure 10b. It was not possible to obtain better results by further adjustment of the corner stiffness. It appears that a geometrical softening

mechanism or material non-linearity exists in the actual blade. This is not accounted for in the FE model hence good correlation is seen at lower loads while the FE model is over-stiff at higher loads approaching ultimate strength. Also, a kink is evident on the FE deflection curves at 60% load which is hardly noticeable on the curves obtained from the test. If certain features in the FE model are too stiff it is conceivable that localized post buckling or snap-through has a more pronounced effect on the lateral deflections of the box girder. It should be mentioned that the overall flap-wise blade deflection shows exact agreement between test and FE model. This is also the case for eigenvalues.

If the accuracy of the local FE-results are to be improved, manufacturing imperfections must be included in the FE-model. For the blade in question, the section at 10.3m turned out to have a relatively large geometric imperfection in the load carrying cap which one would expect to influence local deformation behaviour.

Skin debonding/peeling

Fig. 11a: Skin peeling from cap
Fig. 11b: Reference points not fixed after skin peeling

Figure 11c: Measurements that show skin peeling and corrected cap values

Outer skin debonding from the box girder, see figure 11a, was observed after collapse, but it was not clear at which load this failure mode had occurred. A study of measured cap deflections has shown that the skin peeling starts at 92% of the ultimate load, see figure 11c. The jump in measured displacement is not due to sudden chordwise bending of the cap, instead it was caused by the skin debonding from the cap where the skin assumes more of the initial curvature. The reference frame for measuring cap deflection is attached to the outer skin rather than directly to the box girder corner. Figure 11b illustrates this observation. In figure 11c another skin peeling jump can be observed at 97% of ultimate load.

The actual maximum cap deformation of 4.3mm was obtained by extrapolation, see figure 11c. This is the value that would have been observed if measurements were taken directly on the box girder or had debonding not occurred.

The skin debonding is expected to have a major influence on the final collapse. Buckling capacity of the blade is reduced dramatically once the outer skin and box girder separate. This buckling behaviour can be observed in figure 11c at 100% load, just before failure.

CONCLUSION

Non-linear finite element analyses as well as displacement sensors in the full-scale test have shown different behaviour along a 34m wind turbine blade with a load carrying box girder. The Brazier effect dominates outwards of the 8 m section. This non-linear effect was also found to dominate at the 13 m section where the boundary conditions from the global FE model were applied in a local FE model. This ties in with the requirement for a non-linear global FE-model.

Simulation of local behaviour relied on calibration of the FE-model, mainly due to the variations in production. Especially corners in the box girder show large variations, hence the sub-model did not include fine details, but was calibrated against measured local deformations from the full-scale test.

Measurements supported by FE-results also show that debonding of the outer skin was the initial failure mechanism followed by delamination buckling which led to collapse. When the skin debond reaches a certain size the buckling strength of the load carrying laminate becomes critical and final collapse occurred.

FUTURE WORK

The skin debonding failure, observed in the full-scale test, will be investigated further using computational methods. It is intended to use fracture mechanics based cohesive interface elements in a finite element model. These elements are capable of predicting both initiation and propagation of a delamination.

Extensive delamination was observed in the failed blade and this failure mode was due to interlaminar tensile stress caused by straightening of the curved caps. This deformation is a result of the crushing pressure from the Brazier effect. This failure mode will be studied in more detail also by the use of cohesive elements in a finite element model.

Finally, in this paper only the displacement measurements are presented but strain measurements were also recorded throughout the loading history and will be compared with the FE-results.

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